

Root-zone placement of carbofuran for insect control in rice

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A root-zone liquid-insecticide injector designed at IRRI was tested in 1976 experiments at Suweon and at Honam. Its effectiveness was compared with that of root-zone applications of encapsulated carbofuran and with broadcast applications. At Suweon, capsules applied to the root zone most effectively controlled the striped stem borer *Chilo suppressalis* and the small brown planthopper *Laodelphax striatellus*. One application with the injector at transplanting was equal to two broadcast applications.

Root-zone and paddy-water applications of insecticide to control insects of rice. Variety Palk-weng.^a Honam Crops Experiment Station, Korea, 1976.

Treatment ^b	Rate (kg a.i./ha) of application	Deadhearts at 55 DT	Insects (no./40 hills)		Yield (t/ha)
			Small brown planthoppers at 30 DT	Green leafhoppers ^c at 40 DT	
Carbofuran Capsules	1.0 x 1	0.6 a	2 a	16 ab	5.350 a
	2.0 x 1	0.3 a	1 a	2 a	5.673 a
Liquid injector	1.0 x 1	8.6 bc	72 ab	50 abc	4.130 bc
	2.0 x 1	4.6 ab	14 ab	15 ab	4.339 b
Broadcast	0.9 x 2	16.7 cd	65 ab	64 abc	4.050 bcd
	0.9 x 4	8.1 ab	52 ab	33 abc	4.473 b
Diazinon Broadcast	0.9 x 2	16.9 d	101 ab	74 bc	3.555 cd
	0.9 x 4	5.0 ab	156 b	60 abc	3.757 bcd
Control		19.3 d	114 ab	80 c	3.356 d

^aJaponica-type variety susceptible to common rice insect pests in Korea. Within a column, means that are followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DT days after transplanting. ^bFirst application, 2 days after transplanting. ^c*Nephotettix cincticeps*.

At Honam, capsules also were the most effective. One application of

carbofuran by injector was equal to four broadcast applications (see table).

Number and duration of larval instars of striped rice borer *Chilo suppressalis* in the laboratory

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The larval instars of *C. suppressalis* were studied in the laboratory at CRIA, Bogor. Larvae were reared on 5- to 7-day-old

seedlings of IR5. Twenty-five larvae were sampled at 3-day intervals during larval development and the width of their head capsules was measured under the microscope. Daily observations were also made of individually reared larvae to determine the time of molting and duration of each instar.

Data on the larval head width, plotted as frequency distributions, showed six

distinct peaks (see figure), which indicated six larval instars (L1-L6). The major part of the larval population molted six times (65%) and only a minor part molted five (19%) or seven times (16%). The larval instars of *C. suppressalis* can be estimated by measuring head capsule width.

The mean value of the head width of instars L1, L2, L3, L4, L5, and L6 was 0.28 mm, 0.39 mm, 0.58 mm, 0.84 mm, 1.11 mm, and 1.46 mm, respectively. The mean duration of the larval instars varied from 5 to 6 days and the average larval stadium was 31 days.

Frequency (no. of larvae)

Frequency distribution of larval head width of *Chilo suppressalis* reared on IR5 rice seedlings.

Seedling root-coat treatment with carbofuran

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Soaking rice seedlings in a solution of carbofuran and water gives some early protection against such pests as whorl maggot and green leafhopper. The addition of perlite, a porous volcanic mineral soil conditioner, to the soaking solution extends the period of protection. Suspended perlite coats the seedling roots and acts as a reservoir for further

Effect of two methods of carbofuran application on mortality of brown planthopper (BPH) and green leafhopper (BLH). Variety TN1, IRRI greenhouse, 1977.

Treatment	Mortality ^a (%)											
	1 DAT ^b		5 DAT		12 DAT		20 DAT		30 DAT		50 DAT	
	BPH	GLH	BPH	GLH	BPH	GLH	BPH	GLH	BPH	GLH	BPH	GLH
Perlite root coat	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	100	82	100	18	100
Gelatin capsule root zone	12	20	93	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

^aMortality recorded at 24 hours after insects were placed on plants. Values adjusted using Abbott's Formula. ^bDAT = days after treatment, or when insects were placed on plants.

uptake of the systemic insecticide after transplanting.

The perlite root-coat was compared with the root-zone treatment using gelatin capsules. The root-coat treatment consisted of 5 g perlite and 0.5 g of Furadan 2F in 100 ml of water — sufficient to soak about 100 seedlings overnight; the root-zone treatment involved 2 kg a.i./ha of Furadan in gelatin capsules, placed in the rice root-zone at transplanting in the greenhouse.

Ten adult brown planthoppers *Nilaparvata lugens* and 10 green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* were caged on the plants at intervals after transplanting. The root-coat caused high initial mortality in both pests, but maintained good control of brown planthoppers through 30 days after treatment (DAT) and of green leafhoppers through 50 DAT. The root-zone placement achieved 100%

Rice seedling dipped in water (left), and in perlite-water suspension (right).

mortality for both pests about 5 DAT. Control lasted through 50 DAT. Analysis of plant leaves showed that the two treatments gave roughly equivalent and high carbofuran residues at 20 DAT;

the residues from the root-zone treatment remained high in leaves at 50 DAT while those from the root-coat treatment declined to one-tenth the values measured at 20 DAT. Residues in the stems were much lower than those in the leaves, but they followed the same trends.

The new root-coat technique requires less insecticide and considerably less labor than does the capsule method. While its residual effectiveness is not as long-lasting as that of the capsule method, pest control under greenhouse conditions is immediate and apparently of sufficient duration to protect plants during the critical few weeks after transplanting. Field tests are now in progress to verify this. Because of the possible hazard to persons handling seedlings treated in this manner, the new method would appear to be most suited to areas where seedlings are transplanted by machine.

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